

Feasibility and Strategic Prospects of Developing Dental Tourism in Bangladesh: A Case Study on Cox's Bazar

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Abstract

Dental tourism is a component of medical tourism, which is the deliberate search for dental care outside of one's home nation. Based on the elements of affordability, qualified dentists, service quality, and optimal infrastructure, dental tourism would become more and more feasible. Every year, a significant number of Bangladeshis travel abroad for medical treatment like heart surgery, cardiothoracic services, tests, reproductive treatments, and cancer treatments, however none travels overseas for dental care. Instead, they favor dental care in Bangladesh due to the affordable prices and skilled dentists. Therefore, the purpose of this article is to draw attention to the potential for dental tourism development and to offer dental services to visitors to Bangladesh by establishing dental care chambers in five-star hotels in Cox's Bazar. The paper is based on assumptions and is qualitative in nature. This section discusses the technological, financial, marketing, management, and socioeconomic aspects. The findings of the paper are a concrete arrangement of a dental chamber in hotels to promote dental tourism among international tourists and propose some recommendations to make it feasible.

Keywords: Dental Tourism, Destination, Feasibility, Dental Unit, Hotels, Bangladesh

Introduction

Dental tourism is a category of medical tourism in which patients seek dental treatment in a foreign nation. The top destinations for dental tourism include Hungary, Poland, Spain, Turkey, Malaysia, Thailand, South Korea, the Philippines, India, Mexico, Brazil, Colombia, Costa Rica, and the UAE. Bangladesh has the potential to become a prominent destination for dental tourism in Asia for several reasons.

In terms of medical tourism, Bangladesh is not self-sufficient and travels to other Asian nations like Thailand, Singapore, Malaysia, and India primarily for routine checkups, cardiac treatments, and other procedures. These treatments are highly sensitive, complicated, and expensive. However, for dental treatment, people do not travel to other countries to receive care from local dentists. Additionally, several

non-residents visit their dentists while on vacation in Bangladesh, their home country. The primary causes of this include highly qualified dentists, high-quality dental equipment, affordable prices, sound dental care governance, and risk-free medical care in emerging nations. Dental treatments demand a prolonged treatment process and require considerable time to reach the final stage of treatment. In addition to being an advanced nation in dental care, Bangladesh is also a promising tourist destination. Cox's Bazar is the most popular and developed tourist destination in Bangladesh in terms of accessibility, accommodation and tourist activities. As a developing country with a minimal cost of living, Cox's Bazar may offer the tourists an opportunity to access dental services and reside for extended periods for a significantly lower cost than the other countries. This presents a significant opportunity for tourism service providers, including hotels, resorts, travel agents, restaurants, entertainment services and the creative economy, to integrate tourism services with dental treatment. Travel agents may arrange packages for travelers interested in affordable dental treatments while also visiting nearby tourist attractions. Dental tourism could serve a complementary role if the hotels and resorts set up a dental unit within their premises to accommodate people seeking dental care. It will be more advantageous for international tourists, non-resident Bangladeshis, and immigration. Moreover, the hotel or resort, the destination where tourists will reside and explore various attractions, as well as the restaurants and local community, will all experience social and economic benefits.

A plethora of research has been undertaken in many countries; however, there is a lack of research on this concept in Bangladesh. This research aims to investigate the underexplored potential of dental tourism in Bangladesh and provide viable strategies for its establishment, development, and promotion to international tourists.

Literature Review

Medical Tourism

Previously, dental tourism has been considered as an additional service to the tourists, but in recent times it seems to be more dedicated to the field of medical tourism (Peci et al., 2025). Health is one of the oldest motives for travel (Hitrec, 1998). Over the last two decades, medical tourism in general has emerged as a multi-billion-dollar industry that mainly involves people from high-income countries seeking treatment in low-income countries (Crooks et al., 2010). People from developed countries are going to developing countries for quality treatment at a cheaper cost, this trend has recently been more flourished (Akbar et al., 2022).

Lovelock et al. (2018) stated that, Medical tourism involves the intentional pursuit of medical treatment outside of one's own country or in another country's medical and represents a solution to a problem that has been diagnosed by the health system in home country or originating country (Connell, 2011; Johnston, Crooks et al., 2010; Lovelock & Lovelock, 2013; Pocock & Phua, 2011). It also involves "activities related to travel and hosting a tourist who stays at least one night at the destination region, for the purpose of maintaining, improving or restoring health through medical intervention" (Musa et al., 2011). Medical tourism should be considered from the standpoint of its two fundamental elements; health and tourism (Bašan et al. 2014), since it's essentially a combination of medical treatment, hotel accommodation, and other services in the tourist destination (Babic et al. 2013).

More and more countries engage in the medical tourism industry as importers, exporters, or both. Cuba, Colombia, Costa Rica, Mexico, Hungary, Israel, Jordan, Lithuania, Malaysia, Brunei, Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, Hong Kong, India, and the United Arab Emirates are promoting medical tourism (Alleman et al., 2010; Singh, 2008). The leading importing countries (where medical tourists come from)

are in Western Europe and North America. The main exporting countries (providers of medical services) are based across all continents, including Latin America, Eastern Europe, Africa, and Asia (Smith et al. 2011). Jurišić & Radović (2019) said that Asian countries opened many different medical centers for international patients and have emphasized medical tourism as their national industry (Turner 2008, Sharma et al. 2016). In Asia, the four main competing medical tourism destinations are Thailand, Singapore, Malaysia, and India (Alleman et al., 2010; Connell, 2006; Crooks et al., 2010; Ernst, 2006; Healy, 2009; Heung et al., 2011; Lunt and Carrera, 2010; Ormond, 2011; Wong and Musa, 2013).

In the case of nearby neighbouring countries the following factors motivate patients to travel such as not facing a language barrier, the distance, the stronger the linguistic, cultural affinity and the shorter the distance to the border (Palm & Glinos 2010). Gill and Singh (2011) state the three main deciding factors to take a trip abroad are "competent physicians", "high quality medical care" and "immediate medical treatment." Coțiu (2014) points out six determinant categories: aspects of care and safety; interactions between staff and patient; the outcome of medical treatment; the facilities; the patient's background and the care given to family and friends.

Dental Tourism

The global medical market shows great possibilities for the expansion of dental tourism. Every year, destinations all around the world increasingly join the ranks of promoting health, medical, and wellness tourism (Bristow & Yang, 2015). Dental tourism is reported to be the most common form of medical tourism, accounting for 60% of medical tourism revenue in some countries (Crooks et al., 2010). Chandu (2015) classified dental care tourists into two. Firstly, classic dental tourists are among those who travel to a foreign country to access dental treatment, either for the sole purpose of dental treatment, or dental treatment as part of a holiday package. Secondly, migrant tourists are among those who return to their native country on vacation and then access dental treatment during their visit. Also, there are two types of dental care; general and specialized dental care.

Akbar et al., (2022) stated that there are a few main motivations for dental tourism like lack of advanced dental care in the native country, or the dental treatment not being considered under the local health insurance. Thuy et al., (2019) several studies have identified that affordable cost and convenient access to dental care are the main reasons for the growth of dental tourism. Moreover the low-cost airline travel and the combination of dental treatment with leisure activity at tourist destinations. Abraham & Monisha, (2011) also found that lower travel costs, feasible expenses, and short-time treatments are reasons behind the growing dental tourism in India.

In some countries private dental care is expensive for many patients. The high price of local procedures drives people to find comparatively inexpensive dental procedures. Second, patients unable to obtain prompt access to local dental care look beyond their communities in search of timely dental treatment. Dental tourism companies, mainstream travel agencies selling health-related travel packages, and medical tourism companies likewise use the Internet to advertise 'all-inclusive deals'. These packages include dental procedures with pre-established prices, hotel rooms, airfare, ground transportation, 'VIP treatment', restaurant reservations, and side trips to popular tourist destinations. The notion of dental tourism has become popular in recent years, particularly among Europeans and Americans. The low cost of dental care services like root canals (RCTs), veneers, restorations, crowns and dental bridges, dental implants, and orthodontics in India is the most important reason to opt for the destination for dental care by foreign individuals (Turner, 2008). General dental care includes scaling and polishing, simple fillings, and tooth whitening. Specialized dental care is carried out by dental specialists such as complex restorative treatment and surgery e.g. implant surgery (Chandu, 2015).

Dental tourism companies are proliferating, and traveling for dental care is becoming commonplace in some regions (Calvasina et al., 2015). Many researchers identified the reasons for dental tourism growth. Such as saving money, full rehabilitation offer in a short time span, speed, kindness, humanity, interest in the course of the treatment, the feeling of ease conveyed by the environment and the personnel lack of trust in local doctors (Carmagnola et al., 2012); comparable price level and cost, dentist's professionalism cultural, natural and anthropogenic resources and competent care in international clinics (Enache et al., 2013); (Turner, 2008) (Österle et al., 2009); dental care information access and supporting services (Mustaffa Jaapar, Ghazali Musa, Sedigheh Moghavvemi, Roslan Saub); long waiting lists for publicly funded treatment; expensive costs for private treatment; the increasing availability of competent care abroad; and the non-provision of some services e.g. because of costs or a lack of skills/technology or a willingness of dental practitioners at home; the internet which links patients with dental providers abroad, inexpensive air travel, good and cheap accessibility by air; dental care information access and supporting services (Jaapar et al., 2017); (Österle, 2007); (Turner, 2008); (Adams et al., 2017; Milosevic, 2009); Quality, Price, Hygiene, Environment, Customer Care, Customer Behavior, Places to visit (Olta, 2018).

Dental Tourism Destinations

Turner (2008) describes the key motilities of dental tourism as being from the UK and Western Europe to Eastern Europe, from the US to Mexico or other destinations in Central and South America, and from Australia to Thailand.

Though in Hungary, (Österle et al., 2009) the demographic profile of dental tourists coming to Hungary is between 45 to 60 years old, mostly from countries such as Austria, Great Britain, Ireland, Germany, Switzerland, Italy, the USA, France, Norway, Denmark, and the Netherlands. Most Hungarian agencies and clinics have agreements with 3-star partner hotels or apartments where they usually accommodate dental tourists (Zoltan & Maggi, 2012). Even tourists prefer to visit Armenia due to low-cost treatment and high service quality; they come for treatment, and after treatment, they take a leisure trip (Tovmasyan, Gayane, 2024). Patients from Slovenia, Austria, Germany, and Italy visit Croatia due to their competitive service quality than neighboring countries (Alkier et al., 2024).

But in India, 10% of the medical tourism income is estimated to now come from dental tourism (Kamath et al., 2015). Jurišić and Radović (2019) India's dental tourism industry has grown approximately 30% annually due to their marketing initiatives focusing on all-inclusive package tours (Saravana & Krishna, 2015).

On the other hand, Costa Rica (Warf, 2010) and Mexico have also become well-known destinations for dental treatments (Turner 2008). The main advantage is offering high-quality dental care at affordable prices, including flight and accommodation costs (Barrowman et al., 2010).

The cost of dental filling in the USA and Europe is 300\$ to 400\$, whereas in India it is 20\$ to 40\$ only (Khare & Kushwah, 2019). The Dental tourism survey noted that patients who traveled abroad to receive dental treatment reported an average cost saving of \$6400 or 60% of the cost of treatment locally (Revahealth, 2008). On the other hand, Kotollaku (2024) stated that the average cost of dental treatment for a dental tourist in Albania is around 2196.6 euros.

Dwiastuti & Ratih (2024) found that dental tourism in Bali has already existed for a longer period, and it has a positive impression, though a lack of promotion exists. While dental tourism in the Republic of

Serbia is also increasing in parallel with the global tourism market, it needs more organized digital promotions (Garabinović et al., 2025). Kotollaku (2024) mentioned that Italian patients travel to Albania for dental treatments, and patients select this destination from peer recommendations, though television commercials play a vital role.

Medical Tourism vs Dental Tourism

Medical tourism describes tourism when people travel due to serious need for treatment, which can include diagnostics, surgeries, and specialized care. Dental tourism is a subset of medical tourism; it only involves the people who are seeking dental care such as implants, cosmetic dentistry, and orthodontics-these are often included with vacation packages (Mucaj, 2024; and Mir, 2024). Dental tourism is focused on procedures like implants, crowns, veneers, and orthodontics (Mucaj, 2024 & Sandhu, 2018). Both medical and dental tourism are primarily influenced by the financial variables and the service quality. Specifically dental tourism is more driven by the high cost and limitations in health insurance coverage in many countries (Akbar et al., 2020 & Binoy & Monisha, 2021). As most of the dental treatments are not so serious so the tourists frequently combine the treatment with leisure travel; focusing on the destination that can provide both dental care and meaningful tourism experience (Prastiwi et al.; 2025 & Oltean et al., 2020). India, Hungary, Mexico, and Southeast Asian countries are at the top for dental tourism due to their cost effective and quality dental care (Binoy & Monisha, 2021; & Lubowiecki-Vikuk, 2018).

Objectives of the study

The purpose of the study is to highlight the opportunities to develop dental tourism in Bangladesh and establish a dental care chamber in selective five-star hotels in Cox’s Bazar so that tourists can receive dental care services while traveling to Bangladesh.

Research Methodology

The paper is qualitative and based on assumptions. The managerial, financial, marketing, technical, and socio-economic aspects will be presented here based on some assumptions and secondary data. The target group is tourists from South-Asian countries such as Afghanistan, Bhutan, India, Nepal, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, and the Maldives.

Discussions

Table 01: Dental Tourism Destination

Sl. No.	Country	Cost (local currency)	USD
1.	India	Rs. 15000-60,000	\$201.57-\$806.27
2.	Thailand	Baht 35000-75000	\$1049.79-\$2249.55
3.	Malaysia	Up to RM 6000	\$1415.60
4.	Hong Kong	HK \$ 23000	\$2952.83
5.	Vietnam	11413607-22827214	\$499.62-\$999.24
6.	Singapore	\$2350-\$4500	\$1722.09-3297.62

7.	South Korea	1000000-1800000	\$849.63-\$1529.33
8.	Cambodia	40777704	\$10000.58
9.	Pakistan	Rs. 80000-100000	\$486.95-\$608.68
10.	Bangladesh	BDT 35000-60,000	\$353.22-\$706.43

Source: Dental Implants Asia (2025)

Table 02: Price for three selected dental procedures (USD)

TREATMENT	USA	INDIA	THAILAND	MALAYSIA	MEXICO	BANGLADESH
Crown	385	180	243	250	300	117
Bleaching	289	100	100	400	350	177
Implants	1188	1100	1429	2636	950	706

Source: Lunt et al. 2012, p. 12.

Figure 01: Country-wise Price (USD) Comparison

Source: Lunt et al. 2012, p. 12.

Cox's Bazar is the longest sea beach in the world. Cox's Bazar is the most popular and established tourist destination in Bangladesh. There are a number of places to visit in Cox's Bazar. Numerous development projects are ongoing in Cox's Bazar. The following places are given, which are also under the government patronization.

Table 03: Tourist Attractions Neighbouring Cox's Bazar

Sl No.	Name	How to go

1.	Mahasingdogri Buddhist Monastery	It is located 5 km far from the Cox's bazar sadar/city. This monastery is located just beside the baitush shorof complex at Rakhain Polli. Rikshaw or other transportations is available. It will cost 30-40 taka as transportation cost by rikshaw.
2.	Fish Market	It's located at airport road which is 8 km far west from Cox's bazar zilla sadar. Rikshaw or other transportations is available. It will cost 50-60 taka as transportation cost by rikshaw.
3.	Patabari Buddhist Monastery	From Ukhiya it will take 1 hour to reach by Taxi.
4.	Rakhain Para	Rikshaw or other transportation is available.
5.	Burmese Market	It's located closer to sugnadha beach. It's 8 km from Cox's Bazar sadar.
6.	Inani Sea Beach	Anyone can go there by Taxi or rikshaw from Ukhiya.
7.	Cox's Bazar Sea Beach	On the way
8.	Rubber Garden	On the way
9.	St. Martin	Ships and boats are available from Teknaf to St. Martin by the Bay of Bengal.
10.	Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Safari Park	It's located in Chakaria, Dulahazara union, 215 km away from Cox's Bazar city.
11.	Sonadia Island, Maheshkhali	Speedboats are available to reach Sonadia in 1 hour and will cost 800 Taka.
12.	Prawn Firm	It's located at Koralkhali. This area produces huge amounts of shrimp, prawn and lobster. These are exported to foreign countries and generate revenue. Lots of tourists visit this place every year.
13.	Radiant Fish World	Radiant Fish World is the first live and largest fish aquarium in Bangladesh. It's located on the Jhawtala Main Road.

Source: Cox's Bazar District (Author's compilation)

Hotels in Cox's Bazar: According to the records, there are around 68 hotels, motels; inn and rest houses are located in Cox's Bazar. But only a few hotels are in the five star categories based on the services, features, number of guestrooms, location and other characteristics. For the feasibility study of dental tourism in Cox's Bazar, a few hotels are chosen based on its customer preference, space, location, world class fittings, decorations and quality of service. And they have experience operating a gym, swimming pool and spa, so it's possible to run a dental chamber unit. These are:

1. Sayeman Beach Resort

2. Sea Pearl Beach Resort & Spa
3. Ocean Paradise Hotel & Resort

Feasibility Study

Management Aspect:

The owner will be the manager: The dental unit will be a part of the hotel or resort. The hotel owner will be the owner of the dental unit. The hotel will recruit a senior dentist, a junior dentist and an associate to assist them.

Leasing: The dental unit will be a part of the hotel. The bookings and guest services; contract between the travel agency and the hotel everything will be managed but the hotel but only the dental services will be run by some other entity but under the supervision of the hotel. The hotel will be liable under any circumstances.

Financial Aspects:

The hotel will establish or build the dental unit by itself. It may be included in the investment or establishment cost.

Salary of the Dentists: The standard salary of a senior dentist is around BDT 1, 50,000-2, 00,000 or more. Junior dentist or intern BDT 20,000-30,000. Helper BDT 10,000-15,000. *Break-Even Analysis:* It will require 2-4 years to meet the break-even point.

Marketing Aspects: 8 P's of Marketing Mix are considered here:

Figure 02: 8Ps of Marketing Mix

Source: Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2016)

Product: Here, the product is the dental services, dental equipment and the overall treatment the patient will get from the dental chamber.

The hotel guestrooms, restaurants, swimming pool, gym, spa and other indoor activities are the products for the guest.

The destination itself is one kind of product. Here, some popular spots are identified and mentioned where the tourist can visit during the whole treatment process.

Price: The package price of dental facilities and hotel stay; the destination visit cost or entry fees, transportation, food cost, souvenir cost everything is considered as a price in exchange of the value. There will be two options: One is an inclusive package, including the accommodation, dental fees and all the land costs.

Another one is value on the basis of facilities or service. If anyone just wants to pay dental services and wants to stay at a different hotel or place.

Payment can be done in cash or card combined or separately. There are ATM booths everywhere in the city and on-site booths are also available in a few hotels.

Place: Travel Agency, Retail Outlet, Internet, Hotel Websites.

Travel Agency: Hotels can make contracts with several popular travel agencies to sell their rooms and also up sell the dental services. For example, advertisements in social media about, preparing brochures and posting on websites.

Retail Outlet: Few hotels have sales offices from where they can book directly. So, these features must be available at the hospitals. For example, contracting with few popular hospitals in South Asian countries from where anyone can book appointments for dental service in those specific dental units of Bangladesh.

Internet: Internet can play a great role as intermediaries. Anyone look for options and details in internet search engines. So, all the information about the dental services, duration to stay, specific hotels or resorts, inclusive packages everything should be stated.

Promotion: Advertising, sales promotion, personal selling and public relations are the most effective promotional tools to be followed in any industry.

Advertising: For advertisement print media or broadcasting media can be used to attract mass market. Advertising in hotel websites and other booking sites is also effective. Digital media and social media is a contemporary method to attract foreign travellers.

Sales promotion: Sales promotion such as 50% off offer, if dental services are included with the packages. During off-peak periods, a discount offer or Buy 1 night get 1 or 2 more nights free can be popular among guests.

Personal selling: Personal selling tactics should be implemented on loyal customers. For example, taking feedback or follow up service options should be available for the patients.

People: The Dentist; The Hotel General Manager; The Hotel's Owner

The Dentist: There will be a senior dentist, a junior dentist and a helper to look after the dental chamber unit. The junior dentist can be an intern level doctor also who is practicing under the supervision of an

expert. The helper will assist the dentists in all kinds of work such as taking bookings, setting the patients schedule and other types of assistance. The hotel’s housekeeper will be responsible for the cleaning of the area. The engineering and maintenance department will take care of any kinds of routine or scheduled maintenance if needed.

The Hotel’s Owner or General Manager: The hotel’s owner or general manager’s role is to look after the overall service encounter, service gaps or complaints, profit-loss statements etc. That means, the authority will look after the overall operations of the chamber.

Process: The Service time can be shift-wise, twice a day or only one shift at evening time. For example, Morning shifts: 10 AM- 4 PM; Evening shift: 5 PM-10 PM.

Physical Evidence: The location of the dental unit will be in the hotel premises but in the back of the house area.

Performance: The analytics and variables should be analyzed based on the performance within a specific period. It will help in understanding the actual outcomes and identifying the pain points to develop effective solutions. And measure the return on investment as well as the impression of the guests.

Figure 03: Hypothesis of Cash Flow in a Hotel with Dental Facilities

Source: Author’s Compilations

Why Hotels Should Establish Dental Units

In post-covid 19 situation the hotel industry in Bangladesh is now mostly focused on health and hygiene, and safety to attract guests. Though many hotels are reported to enhance the health protocols, these measures are aimed at general guest safety not for providing any treatment support or arrangement (Rahman et al., 2019; Nasir & Hassan, 2021). On the other hand, dental tourism in Bangladesh is high potential due to its cost-effective treatments, qualified dentists, and modern digitalized facilities. These facilities will attract the dental patients to take dental treatment in Bangladesh, it will cover both the urge of tour and the need for dental check-up. So, hotels can utilize the opportunity by setting up a dental unit in their premises or make some collaboration with neighbourhood dental clinics (Iqbal, 2023).

Table 04: Potential benefits of setting up a dental unit in a hotel in Bangladesh.

Benefit Type	Benefit Segment
Business Advantages	<i>Attracting Dental Tourist:</i> Bangladesh is a potential dental tourism destination due to its highly skilled professionals and affordable costs.
	<i>Increase Occupancy:</i> If a hotel starts to provide dental treatments then it might get more in-house guests and also the income from dental segment; both will directly raise the hotel’s revenue.
	<i>Value-Added Services:</i> Offering dental care as a part of wellness tourism package could make it more appealing to the health conscious tourists.
Socio-Economic Benefits	<i>Job Creation:</i> Establishment of dental units in hotels would increase job opportunities for dentists and some supporting staff.
	<i>Skill Development:</i> The dental unit in the hotel might be helpful for the new dentists and their skills development.
Enhanced Reputation and Guest Experience	<i>Brand Differentiation:</i> A hotel with a dental facility will get a different identity in the hotel industry and among the guests. This facility might make the hotel at the top of the priority list.
	<i>Guest Satisfaction:</i> The convenient dental care service and the hotel’s concern about the guest’s health and fitness will add a different value to the guest experience.

Source: The table is compiled with the author's analysis and Iqbal, M. (2023)

Figure 04: Cost Factors with Dental Facilities in a Hotel

Source: Author's Compilations

Technical Aspects:

Equipment set up: The equipment of the dental unit, the chamber cost. A sample is given here:

Technology: Different technology of treatment

Socio Economic:

Employment opportunity: More dentists will get the opportunity to work full time or part time in tourist destinations like Cox's Bazar under the supervision of renowned hotels. *Stakeholders Benefit:* Hotel owners will be benefited from the revenue generated from the dental services and guest hotel stay, food and from other services spent by the guests. *Contribution in GDP:* Tourists will take appointments from the dentists, stay at the hotel, and take the dental services from the dental unit in the hotel. Besides, they will explore the city; visit the top tourist spots located near Cox's Bazar. Tourists will spend money on transportation, food, ticketing and other services which have a multiplier effect on the local economy as well as the whole economy and GDP of the country.

Segmentation, Targeting, and Positioning (STP) Analysis

The segmentation, targeting, and positioning (STP) analysis helps us to understand how the new product or service will stand in the market, like the potential market positioning and the size of the target market. As setting up a dental unit inside a hotel is a unique and new idea in the hotel industry of Bangladesh so the STP analysis is going to give us a primary assumption about the potentialities and future expectations.

Table 05: STP Analysis

Segmentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Age</i>: 20 or older ● <i>Education</i>: Secondary level to higher level ● <i>Income</i>: Approximately middle-class ● <i>Geography</i>: India, Bhutan, Nepal, and Western countries where the health insurance does not cover dental checkups. ● <i>Psychology and Behaviour</i>: Health-conscious
Targeting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Tourists with dental issues ● Budget conscious dental patients ● Neighbourhood countries with higher dental treatment costs
Positioning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● High-skilled dental professionals with modern treatment facilities ● Financial convenience ● Scopes for high-quality dental care with a pleasure travel ● Unique natural attractions like Cox’s Bazar

Source: Author’s compilation

Recommendations:

Branding of dental tourism destinations: Only Cox’s bazar is considered to be branded as dental tourism destination. Many more destinations can be taken under consideration in the future. Especially Sylhet and Sreemangal have possibilities as numerous destinations are located there with natural scenic beauty. Many well facilitated hotels, resorts, quality transportations facilities and mostly percentages of Non-residents of Bangladesh are located in these regions.

Development of dental units in hotels and resorts: Establishing a standard well facilitated dental unit with trained staff within the hotel or resort can easily improve the number of tourists who are also looking for dental treatments. It can create a different segment of dental tourists in Bangladesh from foreign countries.

Marketing and promotion: Awareness and knowledge build up can be possible through proper marketing and using promotional tools. Website development with adequate information about the dental services and packages, price list, international payment mode and valid contact information all are helpful ways to position the product and services among customers' minds.

Competitive pricing: A comparison can be shown among the countries popular in dental tourism in the world or Asian countries. It will motivate the tourists or visitors to make a wise decision by comparing the prices of dental services. For example, benchmark with India, Thailand or Singapore.

Networking accommodation or travel agencies: Making a liaison with accommodation and travel agency service providers will be a good initiative. The travel agency should develop packages and post in the websites of specific accommodation such as hotels or resorts; travel agencies and is possible in tourism ministries websites. The travel agents and hotels can also participate in the travel and tourism fair to showcase their packages on accommodation and the dental services.

Conclusion:

This study highlights that Bangladesh has a great deal of potential to establish itself as one of Asia's leading dental tourism destinations. The combination of modern clinical facilities, reasonably priced treatment, and skilled dental professionals offers a strong basis for drawing in foreign dental tourists. With its well-established tourism appeal and vast hospitality infrastructure, Cox's Bazar provides the perfect environment for incorporating dental services into hotel settings, making it a convenient and attractive choice for tourists seeking for both leisure and treatment.

The establishment of dental units within hotels can yield significant benefits, according to the analysis of managerial, financial, marketing, technical, and socio-economic dimensions. These include the creation of employment for dental professionals and support personnel, improved guest experiences, new revenue streams, and higher hotel occupancy. Additionally, through multiplier effects, visitor spending on lodging, dining, travel, and leisure activities can support regional and national economic growth.

But the study also emphasizes that for this niche to be developed successfully, important stakeholders must work together, especially the ministries of tourism and health, hotel management, and dental service providers. Assuring patient safety, competitive pricing, professional accreditation, quality assurance, and successful marketing strategies will be essential to establishing credibility and trust in the global marketplace. Overall, dental tourism can develop into a viable and lucrative extension of Bangladesh's tourism industry with careful planning, legislative backing, and focused marketing, promoting destination competitiveness, diversification, and sustainable economic growth.

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